

Synthesis of some New Pharmacophores derived from Imidazole and Benzimidazole

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Heterocyclic compounds having two nitrogen atoms oriented in 1,3-positions in ring are endowed with broad spectrum of pharmaceutical properties¹. Benzotriazole, phenothiazine, diphenylamine and their acetic/propionic acid derivatives also possess pharmaceutical activities². With an intention to get more active pharmaceutical agents, we have synthesised some new pharmacophores derived from these heterocycles. The compounds were screened for their anthelmintic, analgesic and antimicrobial activities.

Benzotriazole/phenothiazine/diphenylamine was first reacted with α -chloroacetic/propionic acid to yield benzotriazole acetic acid (1a-f), which on treatment with thionyl chloride afforded the corresponding chlorides (2a-f). Compound 2a-f were then condensed with imidazole and benzimidazole to yield benzotriazole acetyl/propionyl imidazole/benzimidazole (3a-l) (Scheme 1). The structures were confirmed by chemical analysis, ir spectra and in some cases by ¹H nmr and mass spectra.

Anthelmintic activity : Compound 3a-l were screened for anthelmintic activity by the reported technique³ and the percentage efficacy was calculated.

Analgesic activity : The analgesic activity of compounds 3a-l was screened in albino rats of either sex by the hot-plate method⁴ using Techno heated plate analgesic apparatus. The reaction time was recorded before and after administration of

1a, 1c, 1e, 2a, 2c, 2e, 3a, 3b, 3e, 3f, 3i, 3j, R = H
1b, 1d, 1f, 2b, 2d, 2f, 3c, 3d, 3g, 3h, 3k, 3l, R = CH₃
For NHET, see Table 1

Scheme 1

the test compounds, and the percentage analgesia score (PAS) was measured.

Antimicrobial activity : The antimicrobial activity of 3a-l was performed by filter paper disc method⁵ at 25 and 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentrations, against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus anthracis* using streptomycin as a standard drug. Antifungal activity was tested against *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Candida albicans* using mycostatin as a reference standard. Compounds

3f and **3h** were found to showed anthelmintic activity while **3d** exhibited analgesic activity. The compounds derived from imidazole nuclei (**3a**, **c**, **e**, **g**, **i** and **k**) showed moderate antimicrobial activity.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPETRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS **3a**–**l**

Compd. no.	NHET	M.p. °C	δ	m/z
3a	Imidazole	50–52	3.9 (s, CH ₂), 7.00–8.00 (7H, m, ArH)	227 (M ⁺ , 80), 160, (60), 132 (18), 118 (30), 109 (90), 95 (15), 67 (100%)
b	Benzimidazole	65–67		
c	Imidazole	57–59		
d	Benzimidazole	68–70		
e	Imidazole	170–72		
f	Benzimidazole	160–62		
g	Imidazole	165–67	1.5 (d, 1×CH ₃), 2.55 (q, 1×CH), 6.30–8.00 (11H m, ArH)	321 (M ⁺ , 70), 254 (50), 226 (15), 198 (32), 123(87), 95 (10), 67 (100%)
h	Benzimidazole	172–74		
i	Imidazole	40–42		
j	Benzimidazole	50–52	3.85 (s, 1×CH ₂), 7.00–8.00 (15H, m, ArH)	327 (M ⁺ , 85), 210 (55), 182 (10), 168 (35), 159 (70), 145 (17), 117 (100%)
k	Imidazole	45–47		
l	Benzimidazole	42–44		

*The ir spectra of the final products revealed the principal absorptions at \approx 3380–3300 (substituted benzene ring), 2930–2900, 1450 (–HC–CH₃), 1650–1640 (–CON), 1590–1580 (N=N), 1480–1450 (CH₂), 1245–1200 (C–N str. of t-amine) and 938–659 cm⁻¹ (polynuclear aromatic structure).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in a Toshniwal melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was monitored by tlc on silica gel G plates. Ir spectra (KBr) were obtained on an Acculab-10 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) with TMS as an internal standard at 90 MHz on a Varian CFT-20 spectrometer and mass spectra on a Jeol D-300 instrument.

*Benzotriazole acetic acid (1a)*⁶: A mixture of equimolar alkaline (5 ml; 4 N NaOH) solution

of benzotriazole (15 g, 0.126 mol) in MeOH (50 ml) and chloroacetic acid (11.90 g, 0.126 mol) in MeOH (30 ml) was heated gently on a boiling water-bath for ~0.5 h. The solid thus obtained on cooling was crystallised from CHCl₃, (62%), m.p. 50–52° (Found : C, 54.15; H, 3.92; N, 23.66. C₈H₇O₂N₃ calcd. for : C, 54.20; H, 3.95; N, 23.70%).

Similarly other phenothiazine/diphenyl amino acetic/propionic acid derivatives (**1b**–**f**) were synthesised : **1b** (57%), m.p. 54–56° (Found : C, 56.52; H, 4.70; N, 21.95. C₉H₉O₂N₃ calcd. for : C, 56.54; H, 4.71; N, 21.98%); **1c** (72%), m.p. 158–60° (Found : C, 65.34; H, 4.25; N, 5.42. C₁₄H₁₁O₂NS calcd. for : C, 65.36; H, 4.28; N, 5.44%); **1d** (69%), m.p. 180–85° (Found : C, 66.40; H, 4.77; N, 5.14. C₁₅H₁₃O₂NS calcd. for : C, 66.42; H, 4.77; N, 5.14%); **1e** (69%), m.p. 42–44° (Found : C, 73.97; H, 5.70; N, 6.14. C₁₄H₁₃O₂N calcd. for : C, 74.00; H, 5.72; N, 6.16%); **1f** (64%), m.p. 55–57° (Found : C, 74.65; H, 6.20; N, 5.80. C₁₅H₁₅O₂N calcd. for : C, 74.68; H, 6.22; N, 5.80%).

Benzotriazole acetyl chloride (2a): A mixture of benzotriazole acetic acid (13 g, 0.073 mol) in C₆H₆ : Me₂CO (40 : 10) and thionyl chloride (17.46 g, 0.146 mol) was refluxed for 8 h on a water-bath. Excess of thionyl chloride was then distilled off under reduced pressure, cooled and the separated benzotriazole acetyl chloride was crystallised from CHCl₃ : **2a** (83%), m.p. 158–60° (Found : C, 49.00; H, 3.02; N, 21.45. C₈H₆ON₃Cl calcd. for : C, 49.10; H, 3.06; N, 21.48%).

Other derivatives were synthesised in the same manner : **2b** (86%), m.p. 64–66° (Found : C, 51.52; H, 3.80; N, 20.01. C₉H₈ON₃Cl calcd. for : C, 51.55; H, 3.81; N, 20.04%); **2c** (87%), m.p. 168–70° (Found : C, 60.96; H, 3.60; N, 5.05. C₁₄H₁₀ONSCl calcd. for : C, 60.98; H, 3.62; N, 5.08%); **2d** (90%), m.p. 173–75° (Found : C, 62.15; H, 4.12; N, 4.81. C₁₅H₁₂ONSCl calcd. for : C, 62.17; H, 4.14; N, 4.83%);

NOTE

2e (88%), m.p. 158–60° (Found : C, 68.41; H, 4.96; N, 5.68. $C_{14}H_{12}ONCl$ calcd. for : C, 68.43; H, 4.98; N, 5.70%); **2f** (91%), m.p. 180–82° (Found : C, 69.34; H, 5.35; N, 5.37. $C_{15}H_{14}ONCl$ calcd. for : C, 69.36; H, 5.39; N, 5.39%).

Benzotriazole acetyl imidazole (3a) : To an equimolar solution of benzotriazole acetyl chloride (**2a**; 4 g, 0.020 mol) in Me_2CO (40 ml) was added dropwise in an ice-cooled alkaline solution (5 ml; 4 N KOH) of imidazole (1.38 g, 0.020 mol) in Me_2CO (20 ml) and stirred for about 8 h. It was then kept overnight at room temperature. The solid thus obtained was passed through a column of silica gel and eluted with petroleum ether-benzene (5 : 5, v/v) mixture, and was crystallised from benzene (59%).

Similarly, compounds **3b–l** were synthesised (yields 48–68%) by taking **2b–f** (Table 1).

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